

UTILIZATION OF A THREE-STEP THERMO-MECHANICAL TREATMENT TO MODIFY WOOD PROPERTIES

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1 Introduction

The modification of wood properties using thermal, chemical or mechanical processes has been extensively studied throughout time. The main objective is the improvement of properties, especially natural durability and dimensional stability. In order to achieve these benefits, thermal treatments should impart wood mass loss, degrading and modifying wood polymers. Since these polymers are located on the wood cell wall, there is always loss of mechanical properties, mainly those regarding bending strength and toughness. The utilization of compression combined with thermal treatment has been a usual approach to minimize those adverse effects [1-2]. Additionally, this kind of treatment also improves surface quality and reduces equilibrium moisture content of wood veneers [3]

Therefore, the wood is heated and compressed at the same time, promoting its densification and reducing the negative effect on mechanical properties. There are several wood densification strategies whose results are affected by many factors, namely: wood moisture content, pressure, temperature, etc. Nevertheless, the wood treated this way always houses large amount of latent compression stresses, which can be released when wood gets in contact with water. As these stresses are released, wood dimensions vary substantively and the desired dimensional stability cannot be achieved. This phenomenon is known as shape memory or compression-set recovery, whose origin is in the wood cell-wall ultrastructure and molecular structure [4]. After the densification, it is thereby important to try to keep the compression up to cool down the board, as mentioned by some authors [5-6]. Similar behavior can be observed in wood-based composites manufactured using heat and compression.

Taking it into account, some authors [7-9] have studied the effectiveness of a thermal treatment as way of releasing those stresses and thus imparting dimensional stability of the wood and wood composite materials. It is a kind of post-treatment, and after the consolidation, the wood composite is heated using a single opening press whose pressure is applied just to keep the contact between the board surface and the press platen. When the composite is removed from the press, it is almost fully free of compression stresses. This way, the dimensional instability mainly that related to the thickness swelling is highly reduced.

According to these authors the method is fast, enabling a homogenous heating of the board. Furthermore, it is also a cost-effective method [10]. Some authors have proposed the prolongation of the pressing stage; therefore, during this time, the stress can be released while further resin polymerization takes place as well. The effect of extended hot-pressing on medium density fiberboard (MDF) properties has been recently studied, whereas it was observed that the longer the hot-pressing, the better the dimensional stability was [11].

Nevertheless, in order to relieve these compression stresses it is necessary to heat the board up to reach the lignin glass transition temperature (T_g). At this temperature, the lignin is in a rubbery state and presents less stiffness, so the stress can be released to a lower level. Several other approaches to fix compression strains have been evaluated especially for densified wood, such as the utilization of saturated steam, dry heating and under non-saturated conditions [4]. Unfortunately, they require long time to be effective. In this context, the paper aimed at studying a thermo-mechanical treatment combined with a fast thermal post-treatment and its effect on physical and mechanical properties of wood.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Lumber Material

Lumber from *Pinus sp.* tropical species was obtained in a local sawmill. The material was resawn and 65 boards with the following dimensions were obtained: 300 mm x 150 mm x 22 mm (length x width x thickness). Fifteen boards were selected from this material based on their appearance (defects free), orientation axe (predominantly radial) and number of growth rings. This procedure was used so as to avoid further source of variation of the results. The selected boards were measured, weighed and kept at conditioning room (20°C; 65% RH) up to reach constant mass.

2.2 Thermo-mechanical treatment

After conditioning, the boards were thermo-mechanically treated using an automatically controlled single-opening hot press at two temperatures levels: 180°C and 210°C. A three-step process was used (Fig. 1). In the first step (heating), the boards were put into the hot-press and were compressed perpendicular to the grain (thickness direction) at 2.5 MPa for 25 minutes, during which the inner board temperature was gradually raised up to reach nearly the hot-press temperature. This time varied slightly for each tested temperature. In the second step (thermal treatment), the board was kept under pressure for further 15 minutes.

In these two previous steps the pressure was automatically adjusted because of wood relaxation, promoting plastic densification at slow rate. Afterwards, in the third step (stress releasing) the pressure was released, only keeping the contact between press platen and the board, which was kept into the press for further 10 minutes. The total treatment time was nearly 50 minutes. Four replicates were made for each temperature level and four other boards were kept untreated as a control treatment.

After the treatment the board was removed from the press, cooled down at room temperature and was subsequently kept in the conditioning room (20°C; 65% RH). The board dimensions were measured again and the compaction ratio (CR), which was the relationship between the board thickness before (T_b) and after (T_a) treatment, was calculated according to equation (1):

$$CR (\%) = \frac{T_b - T_a}{T_b} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

2.3 Physical and Mechanical Properties

After conditioning, the boards were cut to obtain samples to assess the following physical and mechanical properties according to ASTM D143-94 [12]: density (ρ , g/cm³) thickness swelling (ε_{sw} , %), modulus of rupture (f_m), modulus of elasticity (E_M), parallel compression strength ($f_{c,0}$, MPa) and Janka hardness (f_H , N). Thickness swelling (ε_{sw}) was the relationship between board thickness before (T_b) and after 96 hours (T_{a96h}) of immersion into water (Equation 2).

$$\varepsilon_{sw} (\%) = \frac{T_b - T_{a96h}}{T_b} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Four specimens were taken for each test. In the three-point bending testing the relationship between free span and specimen thickness was 14 times, while in the compression strength the specimen length was adjusted to keep the required slenderness ratio ($\lambda \approx 13.9$).

2.4 Surface Properties

In order to evaluate the wettability of the wood surface, the contact angle was measured at room temperature ($\approx 24^\circ\text{C}$) for 60 seconds using Krüss DSA30 goniometer and DSA3 software (Fig. 2). Ten measurements (one every six seconds) were taken to calculate the average wettability (θ , °) and the rate of wettability ($\Delta\theta$, °/s) according to equation 3.

$$\Delta\theta (^\circ/s) = \frac{\theta_6 - \theta_{60}}{60} \quad (3)$$

Where: θ_6 and θ_{60} , contact angle at 6 and 60 seconds after drop deposition.

Measurements were performed on the surfaces of four untreated wood samples and eight thermo-mechanically treated samples using the sessile drop method. The drop deposited on the material surface presented 10 μl of distilled water (72.8 mN/m surface tension). A stylus profilometer (Mitutoyo SurfTest-SJ-401) roughness tester device connected to a computer was used to measure the surface roughness. The measurements were carried out

according to the JIS 2001 procedure. The values were measured with a sensitivity of 0.5 μm , scanning length of 12.5 mm and cutoff $\lambda = 2.5$ mm. R_a (mean roughness) and R_z (sum of the highest peak and the lowest valley) surface parameters were calculated according to equations 4 and 5, respectively.

$$R_a (\mu\text{m}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |Y_i| \quad (4)$$

$$R_z (\mu\text{m}) = \frac{1}{5} \sum_{i=1}^5 Y_{pi} + \frac{1}{5} \sum_{i=1}^5 Y_{vi} \quad (5)$$

Where: Y_{pi} and Y_{vi} are the highest peak and the lowest valley, respectively.

2.5 Statistical Analysis

Data on the evaluated properties (ρ , ε_{sw} , EMC, R_a , θ , f_m , E_M , $f_{c,0}$, f_H) was analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's test at $\alpha=0.05$ to compare mean values between untreated and treated material.

3 Results

3.1 Mechanical Properties

Fig. 3 depicts the thickness profile of untreated and treated material. It can be observed that the proposed thermo-mechanical treatment imparted high level of densification. The radial deformation of the growth ring is evident. The compaction ratio (CR) for both treatments was nearly 45%. This value is close to the pressure level used, which was equivalent to 50% of the perpendicular compression strength of the untreated wood (5.1 MPa). Therefore, expectedly, the treated material density was statistically higher than that observed for untreated material (Table 1).

The CR here observed is relatively high compared to that found by others authors [1]. They employed similar thermo-mechanical (170°C; 1.35 and 2.70 MPa) treatment to modify *Pinus caribaea* var. *hondurensis* wood, but observed that CR ranged only from 5.33% to 6.86%. On the other hand, CR values ranging from 10.5 to 15.1% were found to densified veneer from the tropical wood species *Trattinnickia burseraefolia* [3].

This difference comes probably from the automatic adjustment of the pressure during 1st and 2nd steps.

As wood is a viscoelastic material, it can be relaxed under pressure, heat and moisture content. Therefore, the pressure required to keep the thickness profile dropped down when these factors varied. Since the press was adjusted to keep constant pressure (2.5 MPa), the wood was slowly densified when every press adjustment was required (i.e. when wood relaxed).

Table 1 presents the values of density of untreated and treated material. As expected, the treatment improved considerably the wood density in comparison with untreated material. The treatment at 180°C imparted a densification ratio about 42.8%, while that at 210°C, 65.3%. It was also evinced that the difference between treated materials was significant, which means that temperature played an important role in the process. Indeed, the main reason to employ thermo-mechanical treatments is to improve the wood density so as to balance the negative effect on mechanical properties usually associated to common (non-mechanical) thermal treatments.

The mean value of the mechanical properties of untreated and thermo-mechanically treated materials is presented on Fig 4. It is clear that due to the density improvement previously mentioned, all evaluated properties were significantly affected by the thermo-mechanical treatment. This enhancement was higher when higher temperature was used. Consequently, it meant that all mechanical properties of the 210°C-treated wood were statistically higher than those of the untreated material. Opposite result was found when *Pinus sylvestris* wood was densified [13]. It was observed that the most suitable temperature was 120°C, which significantly increased all mechanical properties in comparison with 140°C and 160°C.

It is well-known that the bending strength (f_m) is one of the properties most negatively affected by thermal treatments. Nevertheless, the results here found show that the values were significantly improved: 71.8%~117.2%. Bending stiffness was not affected by the treatment at lower temperature (180°C), but a statistically significant enhancement was obtained at higher temperature (210°C) compared to the untreated material: 51.3%.

Parallel compression strength was also positively affected by the thermo-mechanical treatment, with an improvement between 63.9% ~ 79.1%. In spite of this, it was found that treatment temperature did

not significantly affect these results, similarly to f_m results.

The highest improvement was achieved in the hardness of the treated material: 88.5% ~ 170.4%. Undoubtedly, this result was expected due to the way of treatment. When a hot-press is used to densify wood the material surface is rapidly heated, while the inner layers are still at lower temperature. In this condition, the wood surface layer is firstly compressed, thus imparting the formation of a density profile through the wood thickness, which means that the surface is denser than the core. This phenomenon is quite similar to what happens in wood composite, named “vertical density profile”. In this context, this surface densification can explain the improvement of the bending properties because of the capability of the outer layer to bear higher levels of stress before failure, which consequently leads to higher values of E_M and f_m . Some authors have employed densified surface material as covering layer to improve mechanical properties of wood based composite, such as engineered wood flooring [14] and particleboard [15].

The results presented here are in accordance with those found in the literature. *Pinus sylvestris* wood was densified using three temperature levels and the following strength properties improvements were achieved: bending, 42%; shear, 20%; parallel compression, 47%; and hardness, 242% ~ 268%. Recently, a combined method of wood veneer (*Populus tremuloides*) densification and oil-heat treatment was evaluated [16]. The Brinell hardness of densified oil-heated treated veneers was two or three times higher than that of untreated veneer. Bending strength and stiffness were also significantly improved. *Acer saccharium* wood was densified at similar temperatures (180°C and 200°C) used here [14]. Both treatment temperatures had a positive effect on all evaluated properties in comparison with non-densified material. Nevertheless, the utilization of 180°C implied at similar or higher values of hardness and bending strength than those observed for 200°C, which yielded statistically higher values only for bending stiffness.

3.2 Physical Properties

The proposed thermo-mechanical treatment significantly reduced wood hygroscopicity (EMC) in comparison to the untreated material: 47%~54%

(Table 1). Although a slightly lower value was observed for wood treated at 210°C, the temperature did not affect this result. EMC relates the amount of water molecules adsorbed in the hydroxyl groups of the cellular wall, and it can also be suggested that the thermal treatment reduced or made these sites less available [8]. These authors also argued that thermal treatments can modify the structure of the wood polymers by chemically transforming or degrading them. The reduction in water adsorption sites may have occurred due to the polymers structural reorganization, such as a cross-linking or by wood polymer degradation. The degradation of hemicelluloses (22% ~ 49%), which are the least thermal stable wood polymer, was also identified as the main reason for the reduction in the EMC of thermally treated OSB. [8].

Another hypothesis for the reduction of wood MC after thermo-mechanical treatments is the increase in cross-linking bonds, through which the hydroxyl groups (-OH) of the cell walls are joined together through methylene bridges (-CH₂-), and, this way, the unavailability of hydroxyl groups hindered the water adsorption [1]. Based on the results obtained by these authors for thermo-mechanically treated wood from *Pinus caribaea* var. *hondurensis*, they hypothesized that this mechanism might occur only at a superficial level.

In spite of these positive results, the dimensional stability (i.e shape memory elimination) could not be achieved using the proposed thermal post-treatment (3rd step). The thickness swelling (ϵ_{sw}) of the treated material was several times higher than that observed in untreated wood, whose value was only 4.3% (Table 1). For this property the utilization of higher temperature led to better dimensional stability. The comparison between ϵ_{sw} and CR values shows that wood treated at 180°C swelled (63.7%) more than it was compressed (45%). The mechanism behind this strange behavior is not clear yet. On the other hand, at 210° the ϵ_{sw} value (34.9%) was lower than CR, then indicating that some shape fixation ($\cong 22.4\%$) was obtained through this method.

It has been appointed that one of the most important challenges faced by thermo-mechanical treatment is the elimination of the associated shape memory (i.e. compression set recovery) [4]. Similarly to particle-type wood based composites, the thickness swelling of densified wood is the sum of the natural swelling

of wood (reversible) and the releasing of the compression stresses induced during the hot-pressing stage (irreversible). Taking it into account, it can be inferred that during the 3rd step some compression stress was released and, along with the reduction of the wood hygroscopicity (EMC) led to some fixation of the board shape. Unfortunately, the way the thickness testing was performed does not allow to identify the portion of each kind of swelling in the total ε_{sw} value.

The proposed 3rd step applied here is similar to that tested by other authors [11]. These authors evaluated the effect of extended hot-pressing on MDF dimensional stability, founding that longer hot-pressing had a positive effect. This procedure is different from that tested by other authors [7-9] mainly because they did not extend the hot-pressing, but rather put back the already consolidated board to the press and applied the treatment.

3.3 Surface Properties

The physical properties with respect to surface were also significantly affected by the thermal treatments, as can be seen in Fig. 5. The surface wettability (θ) and the rate of wettability ($\Delta\theta$) were significantly reduced by the treatments. The higher the treatment temperature, the higher the contact angle and the lower the rate of wettability. It means that material treated at higher temperature became less wettable and that the water drop remains longer on its surface. One of the most well-known consequences of the thermal treatments is the associated surface inactivation of wood. Three mechanisms are behind it: exudation of extractives to the surface, reorganization of its molecules, and reduction in cell wall pores [17].

It was observed that the treatment of resinous wood can lead to resin migration to the surface, making it more hydrophobic, which considerably reduced the ability to absorb and spread water [1]. The thermo-mechanical treatment bettered significantly the board surface quality, which became smoother, i.e. lower R_a and R_z values. Similar results with regard to surface quality improvement through thermal treatment have been obtained for wood from *Pinus caribaea* var. *hondurensis* [1], *Trattinnickia burseraefolia* [3], *Acer trautvetteri* [18] *Betula pubescens* [19], *Pinus nigra* [20], *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* [21] *Populus tremuloides* [22]. It has

been also reported reduction in the R_a parameter of thermally treated oriented strand boards [23].

4 Conclusions

It can be concluded that the proposed three-step thermo-mechanical treatment was quite effective in improving all mechanical and surface properties, and reducing equilibrium moisture content as well. The enhancements were derived from the temperature used: in general, the higher the temperature, the higher the improvement. Nonetheless, the proposed post-treatment (3rd step) was not effective in eliminating compression-set recovery, and only some densification strain could be suitably fixed.

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Fig.1. Thermo-mechanical treatment schedule (pressure and temperature through time) showing the three steps.

Fig.2. Krüss DSA30 goniometer, drop profile and automatic measurement of the contact angle.

Fig.3. Cross-sectional view of the thermo-mechanically treated (a/b) and untreated wood (c).

Table.1. Density, equilibrium moisture content (EMC) and thickness swelling (ϵ_{sw}) of untreated and thermo-mechanically treated boards. (Note: means followed by different letters are statistically different at $\alpha=0.05$ according to the Tukey's test).

Property	Untreated	180°C	210°C
ρ (g/cm ³)	0.49a	0.70b	0.81c
EMC (%)	9.7a	5.3b	4.6b
ϵ_{sw} (%)	4.3a	63.7b	34.9c

Fig.4. Mechanical properties of untreated and thermo-mechanically treated wood. (Note: means followed by different letters are statistically different at $\alpha=0.05$ according to the Tukey's test)

Fig.5. Wettability and surface roughness parameters of untreated and treated material. (Note: means followed by different letters are statistically different at $\alpha=0.05$ according to the Tukey's test)